

**SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF IMPLEMENTING THE ACHIEVEMENTS
OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF PHYSICS**

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Abstract: In this article, the relevance of the introduction of digital technologies in the teaching of physics today, what aspects should be given importance in the creation of the national content of virtual laboratories in this direction is investigated. It has been shown that developing digital technologies are also having a positive impact on the education sector.

Keywords: physics, digital technologies, virtual laboratory, platform, electronic resources, computer, content, digital resources, interactivity

**FIZIKA FANINI O‘QITISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR
YUTUQLARINI AMALGA OSHIRISNING XUSUSIY HOLLARI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda fizika o‘qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etishning dolzarbligi, bu yo‘nalishdagi virtual laboratoriyalarning milliy mazmunini yaratishda qaysi jihatlarga ahamiyat berish kerakligi o‘rganildi. Raqamli texnologiyalarning rivojlanishi ta’lim sohasiga ijobiy ta’sir ko‘rsatishi ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: fizika, raqamli texnologiyalar, virtual laboratoriya, platforma, elektron resurslar, kompyuter, kontent, raqamli resurslar, interaktivlik

**ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ДОСТИЖЕНИЙ ЦИФРОВЫХ
ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ФИЗИКИ**

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Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется актуальность внедрения цифровых технологий в преподавании физики сегодня, каким аспектам следует уделить внимание при создании национального контента виртуальных лабораторий в этом направлении. Было показано, что сочетание онлайн-симуляций, цифровых досок, анимации, видео и интерактивных игр по физическим предметам делает процесс обучения более интерактивным и запоминающимся.

Ключевые слова: физика, цифровые технологии, виртуальная лаборатория, платформа, электронные ресурсы, компьютер, цифровые ресурсы, интерактивность.

Introduction

One of the important documents aimed at the development of the higher education system is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PF-5847 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" [1]. it mentions the introduction of digital technologies and modern methods into the higher education process as one of the priority areas of system development. In a word, the purposeful application of information and communication technologies to the higher education system, thereby increasing the quality and efficiency of education, is becoming more relevant than ever. The

educational system is a system organized by the educational process and teaching methods. It informs the system, guidelines and rules for students and teachers. The education system is implemented in educational centers such as schools, colleges, institutes, universities and other educational institutions. Through this system, students will further improve their theoretical knowledge and help them develop their practical skills.

The role of modern technologies in the process of improving national education is increasing year by year, their introduction serves to modernize and develop education, as well as to increase the quality of training of future specialists and to bring education to science. At the same time, such technologies require a revision of existing approaches to educational activities, as well as an analysis of their impact on society and individual social groups. In this regard, studying the digitalization of education and its social consequences seems to be a very relevant area of scientific research.

The field of education is one of the most rapidly developing, promising sectors that are important in the country's development and require modern information technologies and digital resources. Today, innovative technologies in the field of education and digitized resources are widely used. This is one of the priority directions for further improving the quality of education and teaching efficiency. Education consisted of mental work, activity and creative thinking of teachers and students is a multifaceted and complex process. Improving the effectiveness of the lesson is inextricably linked with the establishment of the educational process on a scientific basis and the practical application of new pedagogical technologies. The main goal of organizing innovative activities in higher education institutions is to ensure consistency of cooperation between teachers and students and to establish it in a specific goal-oriented manner.

The use of information and digital resources in the educational system will help you to be more productive. This allows to improve the quality of learning and create convenience for students.

Physics is one of the most complex subjects. Pupils and students acquiring knowledge in this subject require good knowledge of other subjects as well. For example, laws of electrolysis include chemistry, distance measurement from geometry, time of a city from geography, and other such sciences. Therefore, unique innovative pedagogical and methodological approaches are necessary in teaching physics. Today, the level of students' and students' knowledge of the competencies they should acquire in physics is not satisfactory. If there are 25 students in one class, only 20-25% of them are taking the set qualification. It can be seen that there are some shortcomings in the teaching of physics in accordance with the requirements of the time. Including:

insufficient equipment of the physics room with modern laboratory equipment in all schools and professional educational organizations;

low level of use of modern information and communication technologies in the process of teaching physics;

lack of attention to practical activities such as project work, educational research work aimed at developing students' thinking and research activity;

lack of a system for evaluating students' knowledge skills;

In order to solve the above problems, it is necessary to perform the following tasks:

to provide modern educational and laboratory auditoriums in all schools and professional educational institutions by digitizing physical science auditoriums and educational-laboratory equipment;

application of the knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired during the educational process in physics education in independent practical activities, choosing a profession, being able to engage in social relations, forming competencies needed in the labor market;

to direct the development of students' talents, to achieve the ability to apply science and technology development, engineering, mathematics and physical knowledge to everyday life, and to form national, universal human values in them;

education of students' design-oriented creativity by connecting practical activities through observation, critical thinking and logical analysis, inquisitive mind, problem-solving, and innovation skills.

Therefore, taking into account that physics is an experimental science, it is necessary to digitize demonstration equipment, laboratory processes and other educational equipment based on foreign experiences. Digital resources are a set of educational information objects that are used by students for the purpose of mastering educational materials and are presented in several forms. What do digital resources actually mean? Through interactivity, students' understanding of the content of scientific knowledge, opportunities to perform interesting assignments and tasks will be expanded, and the opportunity to study in any part of our country will be the same. Digital resources are useful for science teachers, such as physics or other natural sciences, who do not need to conduct complex laboratory and hands-on activities live, but can instead explain through ready-made simulations or animations. Traditional textbooks are limited in their ability to convey complex physics experiments to the student in an understandable way. In order for the student to understand from the textbook, the teacher's constant support is necessary. The degree of flexibility of the digital teaching system is high due to the processing of digital resources, enrichment, implementation of achievements in teaching physics and many other possibilities. Distance learning can also be delivered professionally online via Zoom, Microsoft Teams, or other platforms [2].

Developing digital technologies are also having a positive impact on the education sector. However, since the Internet speed is not high in remote areas of our country, it is difficult for educational institutions in this area to access educational materials in digital form. Therefore, it will be necessary to provide them with the necessary digital content package. In addition, students may not be able to use computers, as a result of which their interest in science fades very quickly. Readers don't need simple manuals or static PDF literature, they need engaging, accessible, and high-quality interactive content. Today, young people

spend most of their time in the digital world. In such a process, teachers' role is to show students that the Internet is also a place where they can find the learning resources they need to learn. In our time, results are as important as time. Another task of schools and professional educational institutions is to teach students to work. Digital learning resources help to achieve this goal.

Teachers are often limited in their ability to experiment in the classroom. Normal teaching methods are not very understandable for students. It requires the visualization of complex physical processes in laboratory and hands-on activities to make lessons more interesting and understandable, and for teachers and students to conduct endless laboratory activities. To solve this problem, it is necessary to develop national methodological bases and requirements for preparation of simulations of physical laboratories and experiments included in textbooks.

It is not enough for students and teachers to explain the topic in class or for students to fully understand the material by reading from a textbook. Interactive visual simulations filled with step-by-step experiments and workflows should be created to make virtual labs and hands-on activities more accessible. This form is more convenient, interesting and helps to consolidate knowledge. Teachers who want to make subjects understandable and interesting for students spend a lot of time searching for digital materials such as videos, pictures and interactive exercises. Therefore, it will be necessary to create national contents that provide them with digital learning resources. Virtual laboratories are a collection of interactive electronic resources for teaching science. Such ready-made interactive electronic resources can be easily adapted to the curriculum even when the requirements of state educational standards change [3].

Conclusion

Computer simulation of various physical experiments has become an integral part of the virtual learning environment. The situation is not so good in professional educational institutions where physics is not the main subject.

Although the organization of the educational process in physics traditionally includes laboratory activities, the number of hours allocated to this type of work is constantly decreasing. In addition, the usual set of laboratory work is very limited, the instruments are often obsolete, and students are not interested in working with them. In such circumstances, virtual physical facilities and laboratories are preferred. Its various aspects are being actively discussed by teachers and experts in the field of information technologies in our country and abroad.

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